

Synthesis and Temperature induced Structural Phase Transition in Schiff Base Soft Materials

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Research Abstract

The purpose of the research work is to examine whether structural modification through phase transition might result in detection of new potential materials having thermal storage capacity, linear optical property and thermochromic property to achieve the device performance. New phase transition materials with loosely bound systems of Schiff based soft materials will be developed. A series of experiments to the intermolecular hydrogen bonded Systems with required characteristics will be designed. The various characterization techniques such as Neutron diffraction studies, Single X-ray diffraction, Powder X- ray diffraction with phase transition studies, Differential scanning calorimetry with specific heat capacity (Enthalpy, Entropy) and Vickers hardness with elastic constants, will be done and observed the changes in the physical and chemical properties of the synthesized materials, more potent than the standard one. We hope that the structural modification lead to uniform alteration in all physical and chemical activity and useful in the device performance.